

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: WAMBAKA****FIRST NAME: KOSEA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 13%

The author used the following software: (MSWord on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE DILT ACA-401D

1. Which of the following best describes the purpose of documenting potential bias in the design and performance of measures that are used in dissertation research?
 - To demonstrate the researcher's awareness of potential biases and their implications for participant selection.¹**
 - To summarize the development process of measures, including theoretical or conceptual assumptions.
 - To evaluate the reliability and validity of instruments, tests, questionnaires, or observations.

¹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Florida State University: Educational Psychology and Learning Systems Faculty Publications, 2017), 41.

- To describe the organizational structure of the measures section by APA level 2 headings.
2. Which element of an argument addresses potential challenges to the argument's intrinsic soundness by imagining objections and constructing sub-arguments in response?
- Claim
- Acknowledgment and response²**
- Evidence
- Warrant
3. Why is it important to document limitations to a study when writing a dissertation report?
- To provide an overview of the dissertation's findings.
- To highlight the strengths of the research methodology used.
- To explain constraints that may affect the interpretation of the research findings.³**
- To provide future research directions based on the study's outcomes.

² Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 42.

³ James, 59.

4. Which research paradigm emphasizes that reality is socially, culturally, and historically constructed, and researchers must understand multiple realities from the perspective of the participant?
- Critical theory
 - Positivism
 - Pragmatism
 - Social constructivism/Interpretivism⁴**
5. Why is it important for doctoral students to avoid being discipline-bound when conducting literature review?
- It discourages incorporating diverse perspectives, hindering the overall quality and depth of the literature review.
 - It ensures that the dissertation research questions are exclusively drawn from multiple disciplines.
 - It limits the scope of the literature review to only include recent theory and research, excluding older but potentially valuable contributions.
 - It allows for broader exploration of theory and prior research across multiple disciplines, fostering innovation and advancement.⁵**
6. How do experienced researchers ensure the significance of their research questions?

⁴ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. (Los Angeles: Sage, 2019), 150.

⁵ James, 31

- By widening their audience to include everyone interested in their topic.
- By asking questions that are only of personal interest to them.
- By framing questions with implications for bigger issues in their field.**⁶
- By avoiding the consideration of potential readers' interests.

7. What are the four key pillars of effective qualitative research?

- Objectivity, subjectivity, reliability, and validity.**⁷
- Collaboration, rigor, reflexivity, and transparency.
- Participant reactivity, researcher neutrality, scientific authority, and trustworthiness.
- Criticality, engagement, complexity, and contextualization.

8. How best should one handle the views of other authors during the process of writing academic papers?

- Argue against one's self and strive and strive to understand the internal integrity of the views being discussed.**⁸
- Dismiss any views that seem foolish without further consideration.
- Assume that the authors of the selected reading materials are generally unreliable.

⁶ Kate, 2.

⁷ Linda and Marie, 152.

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 14.

- Avoid reading the selected reading materials aloud as this may compromise comprehension.
9. How does critical research challenge traditional research in the social sciences and humanities?
- By emphasizing the objectivity of narratives and grand narratives in knowledge building.
- By reinforcing the idea of neutrality in inquiry and maintaining traditional research frameworks.
- By reviewing narratives as containing power-laden discourses and advocating for deconstruction of grand narratives.⁹**
- By focusing solely on knowledge acquisition rather than questioning societal patterns and power dynamics.
10. How does the treatment section in a dissertation differ between quantitative and qualitative research designs?
- Quantitative research isolates treatment impact using control groups, while qualitative research does not use control groups.¹⁰**
- Quantitative research emphasizes researcher bias, while qualitative research focuses on participant experiences.

⁹ Linda and Marie, 255 – 56.

¹⁰ James, 44 – 5.

- Quantitative research allows for direct researcher participation, while qualitative research does not.
- Quantitative research describes treatments individually, while qualitative research combines techniques, resources, and events.

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